

A SINGLE-PHASE VOLTAGE-CONTROLLED GRID-CONNECTED PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM WITH POWER QUALITY CONDITIONER FUNCTIONALITY

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Abstract:-This paper proposes to solve this issue using a voltage controlled converter that behaves as a shunt controller, improving the voltage quality in case of small voltage dips and in the presence of nonlinear loads. Shunt controllers can be used as a static var generator for stabilizing and improving the voltage profile in power systems and to compensate current harmonics and unbalanced load current. This paper presents a single-phase PV system that provides grid voltage support and compensation of harmonic distortion at the point of common coupling thanks to a repetitive controller. In this paper, the PV inverter not only supplies the power produced by the PV panels but also improves the voltage profile. The presented topology adopts a repetitive controller that is able to compensate the selected harmonics. Among the most recent Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms, an algorithm based on the incremental conductance method has been chosen. It has been modified in order to take into account power oscillations on the PV side, and it controls the phase of the PV inverter voltage. The designed PV system provides grid voltage support at fundamental frequency and compensation of harmonic distortion at the point of common coupling. An inductance is added on the grid side in order to make the grid mainly inductive.

Keywords- Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT), Distributed power generation system (DPGS), phase-locked loop (PLL).

I.INTRODUCTION:-

Among the renewable energy sources, a noticeable growth of small photovoltaic (PV) power plants connected to low-voltage distribution networks is expected in the future [1]. As a consequence, research has been focusing on the integration of extra functionalities such as active power filtering into the PV inverter operation [2]. Distribution networks are less robust than transmission networks, and their reliability, because of the radial configuration, decreases as the voltage level decreases. Hence, usually, it is recommended to disconnect low-power systems when the voltage is lower than 0.85 pu or higher than 1.1 pu [3].

For this reason, PV systems connected to low-voltage grids should be designed to comply with these requirements but can also be designed to enhance the electrical system, offering “ancillary services” [4]. Hence, they can contribute to reinforce the distribution grid, maintaining proper quality of supply that avoids additional investments. However, low-voltage distribution lines have a mainly resistive nature, and when a distributed power generation system (DPGS) is connected to a low-voltage grid, the grid frequency and grid voltage cannot be controlled by independently adjusting the active and reactive powers [5]–[6]. This problem, together with the need of limiting the cost and size of DPGS, which should remain economically competitive even when ancillary services are added, makes the design problem particularly challenging.

This paper proposes to solve this issue using a voltage controlled converter that behaves as a shunt controller, improving the voltage quality in case of small voltage dips and in the presence of nonlinear loads. Shunt controllers can be used as a static var generator for stabilizing and improving the voltage profile in power systems and to compensate current harmonics and unbalanced load current [7]–[11].

In this paper, the PV inverter not only supplies the power produced by the PV panels but also improves the voltage profile, as already pointed out [12]. The presented topology adopts a repetitive controller [13]–[17] that is able to compensate the selected harmonics. Among the most recent Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms [18]–[20], an algorithm based on the incremental conductance method has been chosen [21]–[22]. It has been modified in order to take into account power oscillations on the PV side, and it controls the phase of the PV inverter voltage.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses the possible voltage and frequency support provided by a DPGS converter connected to the grid. Section III discusses the simulation results. Section IV discusses the experimental results. Section V discusses the conclusion. Section VI refers to the reference papers